

Policy Findings for Manufacturing 4.0 in Pacific Small Island and Developing States (SIDS)

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Acronyms

4.0	Fourth Industrial Revolution
ADB	Asian Development Bank
ADB	Asian Development Bank
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CAM	Computer Aided Manufacturing
CPS	Cyber-physical systems
DPP	Digital product passport
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zones
F&B	Food and Beverage sector
FAO	The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FDI	Foreign direct investment
FTA	Free Trade Agreement
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GPS	Global positioning sensors
GSMA	Groupe Speciale Mobile Association (GSMA)
GVC	Global value chain
HIC	High Income Countries
HRD	Human Resource Development
ICT	Information Communication Technology
INDSTAT 2	Industrial Statistics Database at 2-digit level of ISIC
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
IPUMS	University of Minnesota's Integrated Public Use Microdata Series
ISIC	International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities
LMIC	Lower and Middle Income Countries
LNG	Liquefied natural gas
M4.0	Manufacturing 4.0
MSG	Melanesian Spearhead Group
MSMEs	Medium, Small and Micro Enterprises
MVA	Manufacturing Value Added
Pacific SIDS / Region	Fiji, Kiribati, Nauru, Papua New Guinea (PNG), Samoa, Solomon Islands, Tonga, Tuvalu, Vanuatu. <i>This is not an official category.</i>
PNA	Parties of the Nauru Agreement
PNG	Papua New Guinea
PwC	Price Water Cooper house
R&D	Research and development
RFID	Radio-frequency identification
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SIDS	Small Island Developing States
SLS	Selective laser sintering
TCF	Textile, Clothing and Footwear Council of Fiji
Tonne	This refers to metric tonnes (standard unit of weight)
UN	United Nations
UN DESA	United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs
UNIDO	United Nations Industrial Development Organisation
USD	United States Dollars (\$)
VPF	Vertical Plate Freezer
WCPFC	Western and Central Pacific Fisheries Commission

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

WHO: this paper is aimed at policy and decision makers to understand the opportunities and constraints presented by Manufacturing 4.0 for nine Pacific Small Island Developing States (SIDS).

WHAT: countries are racing to exploit Manufacturing 4.0, especially as alternative ways of growth and resilience in the face of rapidly changing world, driven by both pull factors of development opportunities and push factors of not being left behind. SIDS face unique challenges, some of which can be addressed through Manufacturing 4.0, however, this needs to be tempered with realistic expectations - we are unlikely to see SIDS develop at industrial mass scale, instead, **this paper explores niche Manufacturing 4.0 areas for Pacific SIDS-9 countries.**

WHY: opportunities in Manufacturing 4.0 is currently a greenfield and niche area with little research published, though a few organisations are engaged such as Cambridge University (academia), UN agencies and Commonwealth Secretariat (international organisations) as well as private consulting firms.

HOW: a combination of qualitative, theoretical, quantitative and case study data sources informs the analysis and recommendations of this paper. Whilst there are significant gaps in data, SWOT analysis, evaluation of comparable interventions in SID provides a good basis for exploratory findings.

REGIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Recommendation 1:** Kick-start Pacific SIDS Leadership summit on Pacific Manufacturing 4.0 priority areas
- **Recommendation 2:** Promote a “Made in Pacific SIDS” global campaign
- **Recommendation 3:** Enhance regional trading arrangements
- **Recommendation 4:** Map out new areas for regional commons approach to natural resource trade
- **Recommendation 5:** Identify financing sources from diverse stakeholders (donor, regional, private investment, membership etc).

NATIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Recommendation 6:** Set-up light touch coordinating group to define, advise and monitor progress of national Industrial policies
- **Recommendation 7:** Prioritise strategic national sectors to enhance existing industries
- **Recommendation 8:** Increase access to internet and digital connectivity
- **Recommendation 9:** Provide financing for MSMEs to catalyse value chain
- **Recommendation 10:** Develop HRD policies for Manufacturing 4.0

1. INTRODUCTION

Industrialisation has been the engine for economic growth since the 1700's, led by a handful of countries at the technological frontier. We are now witnessing the advent of a new Fourth Industrial Revolution (Industry 4.0) led by innovations in Advanced Manufacturing (M 4.0) which extends the definition of the traditional factory floor to broader inputs such as research and development (R&D) capabilities, interconnected systems of cyber-physical systems (CPS) and non-conventional industrial value creation.

However, this time it is different. Countries that were traditionally constrained by small, dispersed, unconnected population such as landlocked Africa or Small Island Developing States (SIDS) can leverage the potential of Industry 4.0 through strategic Manufacturing 4.0 (M 4.0) inspired policies. Conversely, M 4.0 policies can also adversely affect manufacturing employment with the loss of low-skilled jobs and reshoring of manufacturing jobs away from developing countries. Thus, with the advent of M 4.0 enabled technologies, traditional models of economic growth needs to be re-evaluated.

In the next five years, Industry 4.0 is expected to grow by a factor of ten from \$350 billion to \$3.2 trillion¹. Small Island Developing States (SIDS) could position themselves to capture a small slice of a very large global value chain (GVC) in years to come, through focussed investments in the manufacturing sector (M4.0) but this will require strategic focus responding to unique challenges of SIDS, which is the focus of this paper.

To get a slice of the \$3.2 billion Industry 4.0 pie, Small Island Developing States (SIDS) need to have focussed, context-driven, multi-pronged approach to pool limited shared resources and increase collective impact through both regional and national approaches.

1.1. Summary of Roadmap for recommendations

1. Consultation processes

REGIONAL: Pacific SIDS group should kick-start the consultation process, working alongside donors and international organisations and industry to better understand the opportunities, and constraints. This will be the strategic group with orchestrates strategic vision in years to come. SIDS have limited resources; therefore, pooling resources reduces duplication of efforts and creates diseconomies of scale.

NATIONAL: regional consultation should be grounded in the reality of national contexts. Governance between the two levels is critical to foster trust, openness and buy-in for citizens who will be most impacted by the changes to come. The impact of changes will fundamentally change traditional livelihood patterns and bring them in contact with global knowledge systems that may pose a threat to indigenous ways of living.

2. Development of priority areas

REGIONAL: Pacific SIDS have niche areas which are already developed e.g., disaster management, regional trading mechanisms such as Nauru agreement for joint fisheries management, however, external competition hinders maximal value capture of these sectors. Bountiful natural resource stocks in the region can be preserved through use of innovative green financing instruments such as the \$1.38b spent on SIDS from climate funds between 2003-2017².

NATIONAL: the main manufacturing industries for Pacific SIDS are: food and beverage, fisheries, clothing and apparel and few niche industries, importantly, tourism plays a significant role in boosting demand for manufacturing industries. National policies can readily support existing industries through a combination of innovation policy, market access and preferential trading and funding instruments (specifically for MSMEs). Emerging innovations will need coordination with regional and external support in areas such as low-carbon transitions and seabed mining.

3. Enabling environments

REGIONAL: digital enabled economic growth has the best chance to flourish under a common regulatory framework which brings in pooled funds e.g., research and development and prevent detrimental business and trade practices e.g., large fishing vessels from China.

NATIONAL: priorities areas will need an 'enabling environment' with institutional backing such as e-government, human resource development (HRD) linked to innovation capabilities and funding instruments to support Manufacturing 4.0.

5. MANUFACTURING 4.0 POTENTIAL

5.1. Fiji

Policy context

Fiji is one of the most developed and connected of the Pacific Island economies, with an estimated 842,884 tourists visiting in 2017 and remittances from Fijian’s working abroad making up the largest foreign exchange earners.

Private sector investment in 2017 approached 20% of GDP, compared to 13% in 2013 with a sharp rise in confidence of the domestic private sector and foreign investors with new bank lending for investment purposes rising consistently. Fiji is also the regions foremost trading hub with excellent shipping routes across the Pacific Islands. Fiji has \$7 billion worth of road infrastructure and 1,200 bridges, 47 jetties, 5 commercial ports, 25 local and 2 international airports. The country has a business-friendly tax structure that supports innovation and investment with 20% corporate tax and a lower rate of 10% for companies listed on the South Pacific Stock Exchange.

Significant Manufacturing industries

Bottled water to the US is Fiji’s largest domestic export, other important sectors are sugar processing, coconut products such as copra and lumber production as well as fossil-fuel based products. There is a small clothing and apparel industry based on “near sourcing” strategies.

Industrial production growth (%)	2.8
Labour force	353,100
Unemployment (%)	4.5
GDP (\$ million) nominal	4,891
Population	939,535
GDP / capita (\$) nominal	5,206
Agriculture (% of GDP)	13.5
Industry (% of GDP)	17.4
Services (% of GDP)	69.1
Internet access (% of population)	49.97

Export products

Fiji Product Exports (2019)

Export Destinations

6. POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1. Regional approaches

Recommendation 1: Kick-start Pacific SIDS Leadership summit on Pacific Manufacturing 4.0 priority areas

KEY FINDING: Pacific Small Island Developing States (SIDS) have a lot to offer, and their impacts are magnified when they coordinate for instance the fisheries management in the Parties of the Nauru Agreement. Manufacturing is an important part of the economy for at least four of the nine SIDS in this study (Fiji, Nauru, Samoa, Tonga), even where countries do not have much capacity for manufacturing such as Tuvalu, they still manage to come up with innovative agreements to outsource their manufacturing processes and receive royalty payments (as is the case for Tuvalu designed collectable coins manufactured by Australia). The international community is ready to support Pacific SIDS due to increased understanding of the impact of climate change. Closer to home, advanced economies such as Australia have investment strategies to support the growth of imports from Pacific SIDS. Furthermore, sustainable economies will mean reduced reliance on aid budgets.

ACTIONS

- Pacific Island Forum could be a forum to initiate a task force on creating a white paper to determine interest, areas of collaboration, scope, and resourcing. However, it is worth noting that both Kiribati and Nauru are no longer members.
- Commission the collection, coordination and updates of baseline economic and manufacturing data to enable evidence led approaches. Additionally, appraise cost-benefit analysis for a variety of Manufacturing 4.0 technologies suitable for Pacific SIDS.
- Consult alongside The Pacific Islands Private Sector Organization (PIPSO) to ensure that there is private sector representation.

Recommendation 2: Promote a “Made in Pacific SIDS” global campaign

KEY FINDING: Pacific SIDS are at the front line of climate change impacts with declining fisheries biomass, diverted fish migration patterns poleward – away from the tropics, freshwater salination and loss of coastal biodiversity. Whilst they bear the brunt of climate change impacts, SIDS have contributed the least to climate change. Therefore, there is considerable consumer backing to support livelihoods for people living in Small Island Developing States (SIDS).

ACTIONS

- Investigate the potential to pool together diplomatic resources to promote manufactured goods from Pacific SIDS and identify key messages to connect “Made in Pacific SIDS” with Manufacturing 4.0 capabilities.
- Evaluate best practice and lessons learnt from similar strategies such as the UK’s GREAT Campaign or several iterations of Make in India/China/Indonesia and how they can be applied to Pacific SIDS region.
- Explore the potential for creating stand-alone brand with process for using logo and quality standards.

Recommendation 3: Enhance regional trading arrangements

KEY FINDINGS: The Pacific Island Countries Trade Agreement (PICTA) aims to establish free-trade area between 14 Pacific Island Forum (PIF) countries, of these six countries have ratified and made the necessary domestic arrangements: Cook Islands, Fiji, Niue, Samoa, Solomon Islands and Vanuatu. Once enforced, tariffs on most goods will be removed by 2021. Additionally, PIF countries are also negotiating an Economic Partnership Agreement (EPA) with the European Union (EU) to eliminate barriers to the free movement of goods, services and investments between countries.

ACTIONS

- Create a joined up communications strategy to highlight preferential trading arrangements in the region.
- Carry out a regional survey to establish whether specific industries can benefit from sectoral investments in Manufacturing 4.0 technologies.

Recommendation 4: Map out new areas for regional commons approach to natural resource trade

KEY FINDINGS: There is increasing demand for global consumers to have access to more sustainably produced goods whether this is apparel, food or cosmetic products. Pacific SIDS can agree on effective labelling and enforcement processes to boost confidence with global consumers and to increase value added to existing goods with increased assurance on quality standards.

ACTIONS

- Explore the possibility of regional body to support labelling and enforcement of sustainable sourced manufactured goods for the international value chains.

Recommendation 5: Identify financing sources from diverse stakeholders (donor, regional, private investment, membership etc.)

KEY FINDINGS: Due to the complex operating environment for Pacific SIDS, they have diverse revenue streams, whether this is earning revenues from .tv domain in the case of Tuvalu or minting coins in Australia and receiving royalty payments or receiving international aid, the diverse sources of revenues can be pooled together to support the development of advanced manufacturing industries suited to SIDS.

ACTIONS

- Mapping of all funding flows in the Pacific SIDS region from private investments, donor aid, regional and government spending on industrial development with analysis of how it can be reorientated for strategic, focussed, industrial development.

Figure 10: Do you benefit from any of the following free trade agreements? 226 respondents from Pacific Island Exporters (includes all Pacific SIDS). Source: Pacific Trade Invest Australia, Pacific Island Export Survey 2020⁴⁴

6.2. NATIONAL APPROACHES

Recommendation 6: Set-up light touch coordinating group to define, advise and monitor progress of national Industrial policies

KEY FINDINGS: The lack of data on manufacturing in the nine Pacific SIDS in this study is evident by the omission of their industrial data on the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) datasets (only three country datasets are available, see Table 2). Once regional priorities are in place, a light touch coordinating group should support in collecting standardised industrial data, often this is available for some of the SIDS in this study, but this is not in a standard form and it is several years out of date. Therefore, SIDS should prioritise collection of baseline data to support evidence-led policy options.

ACTIONS

- Provide national representative to support in standardised data collection for industrial development, this should be mapped to existing processes such as the UN's ISIC standards.
- Mobilise national resources to develop plans to collect baseline manufacturing data, in combination with industrial surveys to determine evidence-led policy options.

Recommendation 7: Prioritise strategic national sectors to enhance existing industries

KEY FINDINGS: Common to all Pacific SIDS is the dominance of the food and beverage subsector, specifically coconut derived products such as copra or fishery products such as canned and preserved food. However, there are also unique sectors, for instance, an apparel sector in Fiji, sustainably sourced cocoa bean production for high end markets from Papua New Guinea or sandalwood perfume products from Vanuatu. These sectors can be enhanced by improving incentives and removing barriers.

ACTIONS

- Establish priority national industries based on competitive advantage and determine actions that will increase value add in the global supply chain.

Recommendation 8: Increase access to internet and digital connectivity

KEY FINDINGS: In most Pacific SIDS, half of the population do not have access to the internet, this is the lowest hanging fruit to support enabling environment. The 2020 Pacific Island export survey revealed that 38% of manufacturers in the region believe that lack of international e-commerce capability to attract overseas customers⁴⁴. In fact, most exporters in the region already gain most of their revenues from online website or app-based portal.

ACTIONS

- Support digital e-commerce environment similar to Mauritius' digital ICT revolution⁴⁵
- Increase the coverage of access to the internet for all, specifically, in regions with most impact for Manufacturing 4.0 industries
- Increase e-government services to business e.g. online registration and filing system

Recommendation 9: Provide financing for MSMEs to catalyse value chain

KEY FINDINGS: Medium Small and Micro Enterprises (MSMEs) are well known to drive economic growth, however, lack of access to financing instruments is the main barrier for entry into and sustaining a viable business model, often, they are financed from informal financing such as personal savings, borrowed money from family or friends, or from money lenders. ADB Findings⁴⁶ from MSME sector in China propose enhanced equity financing in traditional sectors, legal and regulatory framework, equity financing for technology-based enterprises and credit guarantee for bank loans to MSMEs.

ACTIONS

- Expand the scope of traditional manufacturing to include financing for technology based MSMEs serving the manufacturing sector.
- Explore the possibility of setting up start-up incubators testing innovative digitally-based business models within the manufacturing sector leveraging capabilities from Manufacturing 4.0.

Recommendation 10: Develop HRD policies for Manufacturing 4.0

KEY FINDINGS: Manufacturing 4.0 technologies will require high skilled labour supply to operate, maintain and understand its functionalities. This will require strong human resource development (HRD) strategies, with specific emphasis on new drivers of economic growth such as digitally enabled business models.

ACTIONS:

- Develop Human Resource Development (HRD) strategies to ensure access to knowledge of Manufacturing 4.0.
- Promote specialised advanced research at postgraduate level to explore potential for Manufacturing 4.0 for domestic firms. Ensure there are sufficient measures for anti-brain drain.

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